

A stainless steel rolling cart with a red ribbon and a 'SPECIAL OFFER' tag. The cart has a metal frame with a flat base and a curved top. It has four casters and a handle on the right side. A red ribbon is tied around the top of the cart, and a white tag with the words 'SPECIAL OFFER' in red is attached to it. The background is white with decorative teal and green geometric shapes.

**SPECIAL
OFFER**

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